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Narrative mapping of the Legendary 18th Century Bokkenrijders in Limburg

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Abstract:

This presentation focuses on the story of the *Bokkenrijders* [Goat Riders; Buck Riders; *bockereyders*], a criminal phenomenon that terrorised the Limburg region in the Lands of Overmaas, County of Looz, and the western part of Germany between circa 1734 and 1795. Since then, the *Bokkenrijders* have appeared in many children's books, television series and film, and the forthcoming 2026 musical, *Bokkenrijders*. This interdisciplinary research draws upon previously underexplored archival sources as well as transmedia narrative iterations of the *Bokkenrijders* legend to: trace how the gang became known as Goat Riders, identify where factual and fictional narratives blurred, and digitally map the geographical reach of the *Bokkenrijders* gangs across the region. The two research questions covered in this conference presentation are: (1) Where were *Bokkenrijders* operating in the Limburg region? (2) How did reports of their activities and affiliations lead to the legend that the *Bokkenrijders* flew on goats at night to conduct their crimes? We investigated how the *Bokkenrijders* came to be known as Goat Riders using historiography and digital humanities methods including close reading of primary and secondary sources and using data visualisation methods to trace the geographic reach of the *Bokkenrijders*.

Key primary sources investigated include trial records from the *schepenbanken* [magistrates' courts] of several communities in Belgian Limburg and published books, including S.J.P. Sleinada's (the pseudonym of pastor Johan Arnold Daniëls) publication: "Cause, Proof and Discoveries of a Godless, Sworn Gang of Night-thieves and Extortioners within the Lands of Overmaas and Adjacent Regions" [title translated into English]. Although this book has been incorrectly documented that the first citation of the *bockereyders*, it is often considered the 'origin story' of the gangs. The term *Bokkenrijders* does not originate in Sleinada's (1779) publication but first appeared in the judicial records of the period. The findings from the judicial records show no reference to 'flying goats' with the exception of one early ambiguous testimony. The historical records, including confessions obtained under torture, contain no specific mentions of riding or flying on goats.

Sleinada addressed the aspect of flying on goats, the gang's name, and did mention that people were talking about this. This suggests that both the terminology and the associated legend of flying on goats originated sometime between 1773 and 1779. Thus far, it was found in contemporary sources that reference the precise term of *Bokkenrijders* appears sporadically, no more than two or three times. The gang operating in the Overmaas region was far more consistently identified by contemporaries as the *Bende van de kanten van Overmaas/over de Maese, Nacht- or Gaumdieven, or Goddeloozen* [translated to: Gangs from the Regions of Overmaas or across the Meuse; Night- or Sneak Thieves; or the Godless Ones].

The secondary data sources for the narrative-focused research include transmedia stories online such as, comic books, TV series, illustrations, blogs, and public interest groups' website. In these transmedial narrative contexts, the *Bokkenrijders* are visualised to be riding goats or horses, which raised the research question regarding whether the *Bokkenrijders* were described as riding bucking horses in the archives and at what point the fictionalised narratives incorporated goat-riding. For example, the Dutch verb *bokken* is often translated as the plural form of buck; however, it is also employed to denote a series of rapid, upward leaps (Cambridge University Press, 2026). In this context, the word buck likely denotes the animal's action of leaping rather than referring to a male deer (i.e., a buck) as Buck Riders also appears in some narrative translations. This suggests that meaning may have been lost in translation. The gang's name has been translated into stories in different languages as Goat Riders or Buck Riders in English, *Bockreiteren* in German, and *Chevaliers du bouc* in French. However, in a historiographic context, the term *Bokkenrijders* or *bockreyders* had not yet been adopted by official institutions at that time, and it appears infrequently in judicial proceedings and primary sources. After examining the archival case files, Blok's (1991) previous assertion that the designation *Bokkenrijders* emerged only among the populace following the persecutions, appears to be valid. Our ongoing interdisciplinary research led to a hypothesis that the idea of nocturnal goat riding likely emerged from folklore in the region. This folklore, spurred by the gang's widespread geographical reach across Limburg and their godless reputation (implying a pact with the Devil) may have fused popular motifs from witch trials, where witches flew on broomsticks as per early artistic depictions of people riding animals or brooms. Thus, the iconic image of *Bokkenrijders* riding flying goats at night was likely cemented by their visual representation on early fictional book covers and the first author, a cleric writing about them, which helped evolve the story into its current form as an urban legend.

To trace the geographic reach associated with the legend that the *Bokkenrijders* travelled by flying goat at night, Sleinada's (1779) early account was used to identify several key points regarding the time and locations of criminal activities. Two types of visualisations were created from this data: a digital map was created using Nodegoat software and organigrams of the gangs' reported familial ties. The map was based on Sleinada's list of accused and convicted *Bokkenrijders* and a series of other online published sources naming convicted or suspected *Bokkenrijders*-often communicated as occurring in three 'waves' of temporally based gang activity described in a similar manner to peak periods of witch trial executions. This mapping allowed for

the further investigation of the legend of fast travel on flying goats (i.e., supernatural stories) compared to their documented physical reach in the region. This collected qualitative data (e.g., *Bokkenrijder* names, date and location of execution, or documented locations of a robbery) was mapped to visualise the distances known to be travelled by convicted *Bokkenrijders*. This mapping revealed that while the various *Bokkenrijders* groups geographic reach was limited to a few “hot spots” (i.e., specific towns), the broad application of the name as a ‘criminal brand’ created an illusion of extensive single-gang's influence, an effect likely compounded by the fact that many convicted members operated within closely-knit family networks. However, historical records have shown different smaller gangs operating at different times in different areas, which during a time of primarily oral tradition (e.g., folklore oral stories) could lead to supernatural beliefs in the geographic reach of an assumed single gang.

Finally, in the context of this year’s conference theme, this project will highlight the affordances and limitations digital storytelling through geographic visualisations of the *Bokkenrijders*’ movement over time based on challenging to decipher primary and secondary sources. The wider findings from this larger interdisciplinary research project on the *Bokkenrijders* appear in a few papers currently under peer review in academic journals.

References

Blok, A. 1991. *De Bokkerijders: roversbenden en geheime genootschappen in de Landen van Overmaas 1730-1774*. Amsterdam: Prometheus.

Cambridge University Press, ‘Bokken’, Cambridge Dictionary, <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/dutch-english/bokken?q=bokken> (accessed 6 Sept. 2025).

Daniëls J. A [pseud. Sleinada], *Oorsprong, Oorzaake, Bewys en ontdekkinge van een godlooze Bezwoorne Bende, Nagtdieven en Knevelaers, binnen de landen van Overmaeze en Aenpaelende Landstreeken ontdekt, met een nauwkeurig getal der Geexcuteerde en Vlugtelingen* (s.l., 1779), 19.